

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THE SOCIAL SITUATION OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE 70S OF THE 20TH CENTURY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8365443>

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Abstract

This article focuses on economic, organizational and cultural issues in the socio-political and economic life of the Republic of Uzbekistan after the victory of the war and the transition to peaceful construction.

Key words

Youth Union, sect, agriculture, cotton, non-ferrous metallurgy, collective farm, industrial enterprise, selflessness, pipeline, bureaucracy, administrative command.

Introduction

After the Second World War, district and city sectarian commissions were held throughout Uzbekistan in 1946-1947. Central Committee of the former Soviet Union work on the implementation of the decision was heated. In the post-war years, the number of Republican Party organizations and their membership increased. In February 1954, the Republican Party had 1112, 7927 members and 138,861 candidates. During these years, "sectarian domination" continued in the republic, and its leadership of the Soviet trade union and youth organization became stronger. Nevertheless, the initiative and zeal of social organizations in the republic continued. At the end of 1957, there were more than a million trade union members in Uzbekistan, who united in 12 rallies in primary trade unions. At the initiative of trade unions, the Republican Society of Inventors was established in 1958 and began to serve the development of the national economy in Uzbekistan. In the five years since the war, the contribution of the republic's youth to social life has grown significantly. For example, 1,148 of the youth brigades and 80,000 of the working youth of the republic declared a march in 1947 to complete the 4-5 year assignments ahead of schedule, fulfilling the two-year plan of the five-year plan ahead of schedule. The brigades led by the Youth Union led the austerity efforts to save public funds, as

the Tashkent Electric Cable Plant saved 130,000 soums as a result of the youth organization's activities. In 1949, the Uzbek youth organization had 280,000

members. They came out with many patriotic initiatives and took an active part in the development of the Mirza desert and central Fergana in Angren construction. They took part in the International Youth Festival in Prague in 1947, in Bucharest in 1953 and in Moscow in 1957 under the banner of the struggle for peace and friendship. In 1951, the movement to collect signatures for the Berlin session of the Caxon Peace Council "On the signing of a peace treaty (agreement) between the five great powers" was in full swing. 887,311 workers of the Republic signed the document. In 1995, 4,023,826 people signed Uzbekistan's appeal to the World Peace Council against the threat of nuclear war. Thousands of rallies were held in the republic to prevent the threat of nuclear war. The interviews were televised. However, in the post-war years, the strength of "sectarian rule" and its

activities to play a leading role, as well as the illegal actions of African leaders and heads of state from other regions have had a negative impact on the socio-political and cultural life of our country. The plan was to increase industrial production by 89 percent and agricultural production by 52 percent. First of all, great attention was paid to the development of chemical, electricpower, agricultural machinery, mining (primary processing) industries. In agriculture, the focus was on cotton. The plan also identified priority sectors for the economy of the republic's regions. In particular, cotton growing in the Fergana Valley, Tashkent region, cotton growing, vegetable growing, animal husbandry, coal, non-ferrous metallurgy, chemistry, energy. In Bukhara region, more attention was paid to the development of cotton, karakul and silkworm breeding. According to the plan, 3,900 mln. The sum was allocated. There were difficulties in carrying out these tasks, such as lack of financial resources, technical equipment. During 1946-1950, 150 large industrial enterprises were built and put into operation in the republic. New branches of industry emerged: ferrous and nonferrous metallurgy, machine-tool. Two large machinebuilding plants

"Chirchikmselmash" and "Uzbekselmash" were built and put into operation. In 1950, compared with 1946, machinery increased 19 times, natural gas production tripled, electricity increased from 480 million to 2.665 million kWh, and the light and textile industries increased by 128.7%. In five years, the total industrial output of the republic increased by 183%. Production of sugar and alcohol was canceled due to the relocation of the Kokand plant to Ukraine.

Plans for capital development in the chemical and housing sectors have not been implemented. However, in those five years, the output of union-wide enterprises increased 4.8 times, while the local industry under state control grew by only 8%. Over the past five years, there has been a partial development in agriculture. The plan was to increase cotton production in the republic to

2,139,000 tons by the end of 1953, an increase of 54% over 1940. For this purpose, Baghdad and Khorezm collectors, Sherabad, Northern and large Tashkent canals, as well as Kattakurgan and Middle Tugai reservoirs were built and put into operation. More than 9,000 tractors and agricultural equipment were delivered to agricultural workers. Thousands of cotton growers took part in the 30-centner movement in the country. Zamira Mutalova and Mehriniso Ubaydullaeva showed great courage in this work. Cotton production reached the level of 1940 in 1947, and in 1950 2,116,000 tons of cotton were sold to the state. Yields increased from 14.7 quintals per hectare (1940) to 21.1 quintals (1950). At the same time, the movement of cotton monopoly, mechanization and chemicalization of cotton is growing. In 1948, with the advent of cotton picking machines, butyphos and mercaptopos began to be used to shed cotton leaves. In the livestock sector, vague plans were made that could not be fulfilled. In the silk sector, a ton of cocoons was sold to the state in 1950 instead of 685.4 tons in 1940, which was a great success. There were problems with the material and technical base of agriculture, such as the low level of material interest of producers, the strengthening of cotton monopoly. In the first five years, 1951-1955, it was planned to increase gross industrial output by 54 percent, gross agricultural output by 50 percent, steel production by 80 percent, and rolled metal production by 70 percent. Expenditures on the national economy have more than doubled over the past five years. Samarkand Superphosphate Plant, Gold-Lead Lead and Tin Plant, Tashkent Porcelain Plant, Chirchik Glass Plant, Kuyibozsuv, 2 Namangan HPPs, Andijan GRES were put into operation. Electricity production increased from 2.682 million kWh in 1950 to 3.880 million kWh in 1955. Coal production grew by 70 percent, machinery by two times, mineral fertilizers by 81 percent, and the textile industry by 15 percent. In the late 1950s, there were 70 industries that combined more than 1,300 factories and plants. However, if we analyze the results of the implementation of the Fifth Five-Year Plan, the annual growth rate of industrial production fell sharply during this period. None of the previous problems have been resolved.

1. The energy sector was lagging behind the development of other sectors.

2. Year after year, plans for capital construction failed.
3. Due to the reduction of oil exploration, oil production has decreased.
4. 25% of light industry enterprises did not meet production targets.
5. Productivity growth has slowed.

The plans were implemented mainly due to the rapid development of the national economy. Despite a 2.3-fold increase in capital investment in the national economy over five years, gross industrial output has barely increased 1.6-fold and labor productivity 1.2-fold. Evidence suggests that capital

investment has not been as effective. 6. The location of the productive forces in the republic was uneven. For example, in 1955 the share of Tashkent region in the gross industrial output was 39.8%, while the share of Surkhandarya region was 1.7%. In February 1954, the Central Committee of the former ruling party and the government of the former Soviet Union adopted a resolution "On further development of cotton growing in the Uzbek SSR in 1954-1958", which focused on improving water management, mechanization of cotton growing, training. was given. In 1958, the MTS was rebuilt and many cars and tractors were sold to the collective farms. Between 1953 and 1955, 130,000 hectares of new land were developed. The number of tractors in agriculture increased by 40% from

33.5 thousand (1951) to 46.8 thousand (1955). The number of cotton picking machines at MTS increased from 3.3 thousand to 15.1 thousand. Although 12,716.1 thousand tons of cotton were sold to the state in five years, the cotton production plan for 1951-1956 was not fulfilled. According to the seven-year plan for 1959-1965, national income was to increase by 62- 65% in 1965 compared to 1958, and agricultural output by 70%. It was planned to build and put into operation 164 large industrial enterprises for capital construction. Thanks to the selfless labor of workers and employees, the gross industrial output in 1965 increased 1.8 times as much as in 1959. The share of energy, chemistry, machinery and non-ferrous metallurgy in social production increased by 18-28%. Gas production increased from 126 million cubic meters in 1958 to 16.475 million cubic meters in 1965. The Bukhara-Uralsk main pipeline has been built and put into operation. In seven years, exports of Uzbek products (through the center) to foreign countries increased by 54%. By 1963, there were 1,400 collective farms and 182 state farms in Uzbekistan. Karshi, Sherabad, Amu Bukhara main canals were built and put into operation, new lands were developed. Some work has also been done in the field of agricultural mechanization. In 1964, 64,000 tractors, 16.4 thousand cotton pickers and 59.6 thousand cultivators were sold to collective and state farms. In seven years, 96,000 tractors have been trained with a focus on

mechanization. The names of such mechanics as Tursunoy Ahunova, Javod Kochiev, M.Umrzakov were famous in those years. Despite the above, the efficiency of enterprises was low. The seven-year agricultural target has not been met. The quality of industrial products began to lag behind world standards. The problem of the Aral Sea began. Opportunities for rapid economic development were running out. The economic reforms that began in seven years have not been completed. In addition, in the 70s and 80s, the administrative command in the management of the national economy became stronger. The evils of bureaucracy and subjectivism have become widespread. The decline in agricultural development in the 1970s and 1980s can be seen in the following figures.

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